

Effects of herbicides on rice seed coated with activated carbon and direct seeded. Second crop, 1977, Chiayi, Taiwan.

Herbicide	Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Weed control ^a		Rice toxicity ^b		Yield (t/ha) ^c	
		With carbon	Without carbon	With carbon	Without carbon	With carbon	Without carbon
Terbuchlor	0.3	1.7	1.1	5.8	8.3	5.2 ab	3.1 c
Benzglycereth (WL29226)	0.5	4.3	4.3	2.0	2.1	5.7 a	5.1 ab
Piperophos/ dimethametryn	0.5/ 0.5	1.9	1.7	3.4	5.6	5.4 ab	4.5 bc
Piperophos/ 2,4-D IPE	0.5/ 0.5	8.0	8.2	3.3	4.4	5.6 ab	5.2 ab
Perfluidone/ 2,4-D IPE	1.0/ 0.25	8.6	8.8	4.8	5.1	5.3 ab	5.5 ab
Untreated control	–	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	4.9 ab	4.8 ab

^a Rated at 15 days after herbicide application: 1 = no control, 10 = excellent weed control.

^b Rated at 15 days after herbicide application: 1 = no control, 10 = complete kill of rice.

^c Any two means with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

piperophos/dimethametryn, and piperophos/2,4-D IPE. Herbicides with protectant gave higher yields than those without; the degree of yield increase was more pronounced in herbicides that are more toxic to rice. Without protectant, plots treated with the highly toxic terbuchlor and piperophos/dimethametryn

gave lower yields than the untreated control; the difference for terbuchlor was significant at the 0.05% level. The untreated control with carbon-coated seeds also yielded higher than that without carbon coating, suggesting that activated carbon has beneficial effects other than as a herbicide protectant.

Nitrogen application as high as 180 kg N/ha resulted in a positive yield response and improved all characters observed (effective tillers, panicle length, test weight, and flag leaf area). The uptake of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in plants increased as nitrogen level increased; uptake of all nutrients was maximum at 180 kg N/ha. The protein in grain increased with increasing nitrogen level; it ranged from 8.97 to 11.20%.

With every increase in nitrogen level, grain yield increased significantly. At 0, 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha levels the mean yields were 4.3, 5.5, 6.2, and 6.7 t/ha, respectively. The percentage increases in yield over the control for 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha were 28, 46, and 57, respectively. The responses per kilogram of nitrogen at 60, 120, and 180 kg/ha were 21, 16, and 14 kg of paddy grain, respectively.

Nitrogen applied through urea gave the maximum grain yield (6.3 t/ha), followed by the urea + CAN combination (6.1 t/ha) and CAN (6.0 t/ha). Although the forms of nitrogen did not produce significant differences in grain yield, urea returned a higher net profit per hectare and was most economical. **W**

Soil and crop management

Effect of levels and sources of nitrogen on Jaya

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Nitrogen fertilization, one of the most effective production inputs for rice, is expensive in Asia. To increase rice yields, not only is the optimum quantity of nitrogen important; suitable sources must also be considered. A field experiment was designed through the European Nitrogen Service program at J. N. Agricultural University, Jabalpur, M. P., India, to determine optimum and profitable doses of nitrogen supplied

through suitable sources to Jaya, a high yielding dwarf indica variety.

The soil of the experimental area was sandy clay loam, low in available nitrogen (156 kg/ha), medium in available P₂O₅ (44 kg/ha), and high in available K₂O (300 kg/ha). The soil's pH was 7.0. Four levels of nitrogen (0, 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha) and three sources (urea, calcium ammonium nitrate [CAN], and urea as basal with CAN topdressed) were used. The nitrogen was applied in 3 split doses: 50% as basal, 25% at active tillering stage, and the remaining 25% at panicle initiation. Among the data determined were ancillary characters; nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium content in plants; and protein content of the grain.

The pinch method of dibbling rice in a paste of cow dung under wet conditions in southern Kerala, India

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A peculiar system of sowing rice - dibbling seeds in a paste of cow dung under wet conditions - has long been practiced in parts of southern Kerala.

After the final puddling, the farmer levels the field with a leveling board, leaving only a minimum amount of water. The field is left that way overnight (15–18 hours) to allow the sediments to settle. The next morning the standing water is drained. Raised beds about 2 to 2.5 m wide are then made by opening small furrows 10-cm deep with spades to allow the inlet and drainage of irrigation water during crop growth. The individual beds are then leveled with a device made